

FIRST AID FOR SHOCK

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Abstract: *Our life, unfortunately, is not always calm and measured - sometimes situations occur in it that lead to shock - a state when the body reacts pathologically to stimuli. There are several types of shock - the classification depends on which organ system disrupts its work. In addition, shock can have different degrees of severity - from the first (compensatory) to the fourth (irreversible). Also, experts operate with the concept of "shock index", which will help to establish the recording of tonometer readings.*

Key words: *shock, first aid, medical treatment, symptoms*

Since the state of shock is a threat to health, and even to human life, it is necessary to start providing assistance in a timely manner, and to do it right.

What does first aid for shock include?

Naturally, the first action is to call specialists who will provide medical assistance to the victim. However, while waiting for them, one should not be idle. Emergency care for shock primarily requires the termination of the traumatic factor. If the victim is bleeding, try to stop it.

In further emergency care for shock, lay the victim down, placing his legs on a raised platform, ease breathing, and warm.

Shock is a severe condition where the cardiovascular system cannot keep up with the body's blood supply, usually due to low blood pressure and damage to cells or tissues.

Causes of shock

Shock can be caused by a condition in the body where blood circulation is dangerously low, such as heart disease (heart attack or heart failure), large blood loss (hemorrhage), dehydration, severe allergic reactions, or blood poisoning (sepsis). Classification of shock includes: cardiogenic shock (associated with cardiovascular problems), hypovolemic shock (caused by low blood volume), anaphylactic shock (caused by allergic reactions), septic shock (caused by infections), neurogenic shock

(nervous system disorders). Shock is a life-threatening condition and requires immediate medical treatment, and emergency care is not ruled out. The patient's condition in shock can deteriorate rapidly, be prepared for primary resuscitation.

Symptoms

Symptoms of shock may include fear or excitement, blue lips and nails, chest pain, confusion, cold, wet skin, reduced or stopped urination, dizziness, fainting, low blood pressure, paleness, excessive sweating, rapid heart rate, shallow breathing, unconsciousness, weakness.

What can you do? First aid for shock

Check the victim's airway and give artificial respiration if necessary.

If the patient is conscious and has no injuries to the head, limbs, back, lay him on his back, while the legs should be raised by 30 cm; keep your head down. If the patient has received an injury in which the raised legs cause a feeling of pain, then do not raise them. If the patient has received a severe injury to the spine, leave him in the position in which he was found, without turning over, and provide first aid by treating wounds and cuts (if any). The person should remain warm, loosen tight clothing, do not give the patient any food or drink. If the patient is vomiting or drooling, turn his head to the side to ensure the outflow of vomit (only if there is no suspicion of a spinal cord injury). If, nevertheless, there is a suspicion of damage to the spine and the patient is vomiting, it is necessary to turn it over, fixing the neck and back.

Call an ambulance and continue to monitor vital signs (temperature, pulse, respiratory rate, blood pressure) until help arrives.

Preventive measures

Shock is easier to prevent than to treat. Prompt and timely treatment of the underlying cause will reduce the risk of severe shock. First aid will help control the state of shock.

During shock, two successively developing phases are distinguished: excitation and inhibition. The excitation phase occurs after the injury, sometimes it may be absent. In this phase, the victim is mobile, verbose, pale. The pupils are dilated, the pulse is frequent, and blood pressure is increased. The consciousness of the victim is saved. The severity of damage in this phase is difficult to determine. You can make a mistake and underestimate the condition of the victim.

The condition of the victim is rapidly deteriorating, so it is urgent to take anti-shock measures at the scene. This is especially important in children, as their shock comes faster and is more severe.

When carrying out anti-shock measures, first of all, it is necessary to stop the bleeding. Give the victim painkillers and sedatives (analgin, pentalgin, aspirin, and valerian or peony infusion). Create rest for the damaged area of the body using standard or improvised splints. Apply a sterile dressing to the wound. In cases of chest

- injury complicated by pneumothorax (air entering the chest), apply an airtight bandage. Apply a plastic bag with ice or cold water to the damaged area. Give the victim (if possible) a small amount of hot tea or coffee, wrap him in a blanket. Urgently and very carefully transport the victim to the nearest medical facility.

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